

VISCOSITY AND AXIAL RATIO OF SHELLAC

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Molecular axial ratios for hard resin, soft resin and dewaxed shellac have been calculated from viscometric data using different solvents (EtOH, PrOH and BuOH). The ratio 10.3 for dewaxed shellac has been found to be a weighted average of the values for hard resin (11.3) and soft resin (7.8).

The effect of good and bad solvents as also of solvents-precipitant mixtures on the intrinsic viscosity of shellac and the variation of this with temperature has been studied. From a consideration of these data in the light of Alfrey, Bartovics and Mark's theory, it has been possible to conclude that shellac molecules are not flexible.

In a previous communication (Basu, this issue, p. 148) it has been shown that shellac resin dissolves molecularly in dilute solutions and further that the dissolved particles are not solvated at least up to 4% concentration. These observations make possible the calculation of molecular size of the dissolved unit from viscometric data. Accordingly, in the present paper viscometric data have been employed in determining the axial ratio, *i. e.* the ratio of length to breadth of the dissolved units.

Einstein's equation connecting the viscosity of suspensions with the size of the suspended particles, which in a sense forms the basis of the present investigation, may be written as,

$$\eta/\eta_0 = (1 + 2.5\phi) \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where η is the viscosity of the solution, η_0 that of the solvent and ϕ , the volume fraction occupied by the particles in solution. This equation may be transformed into the following form

$$\eta - \eta_0/\eta_0 \text{ or } \eta_{sp} = 2.5\phi \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

The interesting point to note about this equation is that though originally intended to apply to colloidal suspensions only, it has been found to hold good for some homogeneous solutions, *e.g.*, stearic acid solution (Hollihan and Briggs, *J Phys. Chem.*, 1942, 46, 685), where the size of the solute particles is much bigger than that of the solvent. Einstein's equation, however, applies only to spherical particles and has been generalised by Sakurda (*Kolloid Z.*, 1934, 68, 2) to include cases of non-spherical particles. Sakurda's equation is

$$\eta_{sp} = K\phi \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where K = a constant depending on the shape of the particle. The value of K can be obtained from the slope of the curves $\eta_{sp} - \phi$, ϕ being further defined as $\frac{cV}{100}$,

where c = concentration in grams per 100 c. c. of the solvent, and V = partial specific volume of the solute.

A further attack on the problem by the hydrodynamical method, first attempted by Jeffery (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923, 102, A, 163) and later on continued by Eisenschitz (Dissertation, Vienna, 1937), Kuhn (*Kolloid Z.*, 1933, 62, 269) and others resulted in a general relation by Guth, from which Kuhn deduced as a special case the following equation

$$\eta = \eta_0 \left(1 + \frac{5}{2} \phi + \frac{1}{16} \left(\frac{a}{b} \right)^2 \phi + \dots \right) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

where a = half-axis major and b = half-axis minor. For a dilute solution the very small interaction between the dissolved units allows the higher terms in equation (4) to be neglected, so that it may be written as

$$\eta_{sp} = 2.5\phi + \frac{1}{16} \left(\frac{a}{b} \right)^2 \phi \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

Comparing (3) with (5) we obtain

$$K = 2.5 + \frac{1}{16} \left(\frac{a}{b} \right)^2 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

The conditions under which Kuhn's equation should apply will be taken up in a later section.

As already stated, K may be obtained from the slope of the curve $\eta - \phi$, whence by using equation (6) the value of the axial ratio of the dissolved units may be calculated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Apparatus and Method.—The soft and hard resins were separated by the simple method proposed by Palit (*J. Indian Chem. Soc. Ind. & News Ed.*, 1942, 5, 25). Finely ground dewaxed shellac (100 mesh, 100 g.) was treated with 800 c. c. of 1:1 ethyl acetate-benzene mixture, allowed to stand for an hour with occasional stirring. The solution was then filtered through a piece of coarse linen. The residue was again treated with a fresh quantity of ethyl acetate-benzene mixture to free it from the adhering soft resin, and filtered after 15 to 20 minutes. The hard resin, left undissolved, was dried, dissolved in alcohol and reprecipitated with ether. Soft resin was recovered from ethyl acetate-benzene solution and dried in a vacuum oven. The analytical data for the hard resin and soft resin, thus obtained, and for the dewaxed shellac, used in the experiments, are given below.

	Ether soluble.	A. V.	Iodine value.
Dewaxed shellac	29.4%	70.3	14.14
Hard resin	2.68	64.11	12.4
Soft resin	99.06	97	15.1

The samples were then dried by the same method as described in a previous paper (Basu, *loc. cit.*). Since complete elimination of moisture from the sample is impossible it is desirable that the absolute amount of

moisture in different solutions should be constant, to ensure a uniform variation in viscosity in every case, on account of this factor. This was attained by first preparing a concentrated mother solution which could then be diluted to required concentrations.

The viscosity measurements were carried out at 30° with an Ostwald viscometer having the inner capillary diameter of 0.8 mm. and length 6 cm. The density measurements were made with a pyknometer of 4.661 c.c. capacity.

In the previous communication (Basu, *loc. cit.*) it was shown that the partial specific volume remains constant up to a concentration of 4%. Hence the present study has been restricted to concentration up to 4% only. The specific viscosity η_{sp} was plotted against $cV/100$ as shown in Fig. 1, the corresponding values being given in Table I.

Fig. 1.

- 1. Hard resin.
- 2. Dewaxed shellac.
- 3. Soft resin.

TABLE I

Shellac %	$\eta_{rel.}$	$\eta_{sp.}$	Solvent: Ethyl alcohol		K.	Axial ratio a/b.
			Mean V.	$cV/100.$		
			Dewaxed Shellac.			
1	1.0853	0.0853		0.00930	9.17	10.3
2	1.1712	0.1712	0.930	0.01860		
3	1.2627	0.2627		0.02790		
4	1.3459	0.3459		0.03720		
			Hard Resin.			
0.8725	1.0909	0.0909		0.00815	11.03	11.7
1.745	1.1825	0.1825	0.934	0.01630		
2.6175	1.2829	0.2829		0.02445		
3.490	1.3850	0.3850		0.03260		
			Soft Resin.			
0.833	1.0554	0.0554		0.008633	6.39	7.8
1.887	1.1051	0.1051	0.925	0.017460		
2.862	1.1569	0.1569		0.026481		
3.776	1.2398	0.2398		0.034920		

The value of the axial ratio for shellac is found to be nearly a weighted average of those of hard and soft resin.

The values of the axial ratio for dewaxed shellac in two other solvents, viz., *n*-butyl alcohol and *n*-propyl alcohol are given in Table II and plotted in Fig. 2.

TABLE II

Shellac %.	η rel.	η_{sp} .	Solvent : Butyl alcohol.			K.	Axial ratio a/b .
			Mean V.	$cV/100$.			
1	1.089	0.892		0.00941			
2	1.179	0.1792	0.941	0.01882	9.5	10.44	
3	1.269	0.2698		0.2823			
4	1.360	0.3601		0.03764			
Solvent : <i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol							
1	1.087	0.0876		0.00938			
2	1.176	0.1767	0.938	0.01872	9.3	10.40	
3	1.264	0.2645		0.02814			
4	1.353	0.3537		0.03752			

It will be seen that a/b ratio for dewaxed shellac in ethyl alcohol, *n*-butyl alcohol and *n*-propyl alcohol is constant within 1%.

DISCUSSION

Calculation of the axial ratio from viscometric data was first undertaken by Mark (*Chem. Ind.*, 1934, 31, Spec. No. 788-791) for hydrocarbons: (C_{27} -) in dilute solutions. Since then Kuhn's approximate equation has been applied by Fahey and Green (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 3039) to the case of glycine, casein and horse serum protein, by Lauffer (*Science*, 1938, 87, 469) and Frampton and Neurath (*ibid.*, 1938, 87, 468) to the case of tobacco mosaic virus, by Polson to a number of proteins, the last author employing also Arrhenius' equation for estimating viscosity increment at infinite dilution.

Applicability of Kuhn's equation, which depends in the first place on the persistence of a linear relationship between η and concentration, is limited by certain other conditions, viz., (1) a/b value should be small; (2) the particles should not be flexible; and (3) no solvation of the particle should take place.

(1) As to the first condition, it has been found (Eirich, *Report on Progress in Physics*, 1940, VII, 342) that for $a/b=20$, the linear relationship between $\eta_{sp}-\phi$ does not persist beyond a very low concentration corresponding to $\eta_{sp}=0.025$ and that for $a/b=140$, the limit of validity is reached at as low a concentration as $c=0.015$. In case of shellac, however, persistence of linearity at a relatively high concentration of 4% corresponding to $\eta_{sp}=0.3459$ definitely indicates a value for a/b , much lower than 20, and hence the applicability of Kuhn's equation,

(2) The next point namely that shellac molecules are not flexible under the conditions of the present experiment could be tested in the light of the theory of Alfrey, Bartovics and Mark (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 1667). According to this theory, in a bad solvent the segments of a flexible macromolecule attract one another, leading to a coiling up of the molecule and setting up of intramolecular agglomeration. On the other hand, for a good solvent the molecules of the solute will be surrounded in the solution by a solvent pull tending to prevent contact between the segments of the same polymer and thereby help maintain an uncurled configuration. This will result in a higher intrinsic viscosity in good solvents and a lower one in bad solvents. Further, an increase in temperature will cause curling up of the particles to approach an intermediate state, so that with a good solvent the intrinsic viscosity should decrease, while with a poor one it should increase. A valid confirmation of the above theory and the effects predicted therefrom have been obtained by Alfrey, Bartovics and Mark (*loc. cit.*) in the case of rubber, polystyrene and cellulose acetate. The contrary observation in case of shellac, namely that its intrinsic viscosity in various good solvents, (such as ethyl alcohol, *n*-propyl alcohol, *n*-butyl alcohol, *n*-butyric acid and ethyl lactate), is nearly constant and is very much lower than that in acetophenone, benzaldehyde and butyraldehyde, a number of bad solvents, indicates according to the above theory, that shellac molecules are not flexible.

Further, since it appears highly improbable that even in the various so-called good solvents the molecules will be coiled up to the same extent, the constancy of intrinsic viscosity, as well as of the axial ratio in such solvents, is an additional confirmation of the view that shellac molecules are not flexible, or more correctly, the flexibility of the molecule is negligible.

Viewed from a still another point, if a good solvent be mixed with a precipitant, the resulting mixture may be taken as less favourable to the dissolution of the particles than the pure solvent. A dilute solution of a flexible high polymer in a solvent-precipitant mixture should therefore exhibit a lower viscosity than a dilute solution of the same substance in a pure solvent. This point has been experimentally verified by the above-mentioned authors with rubber, polystyrene and cellulose acetate. In the present case the curves η/η_0 (see Fig. 3) against the respective percentages of benzene and cyclohexane in a 4% solution of shellac in ethyl alcohol show that η/η_0 rises continuously instead of diminishing, further supporting the view that shellac molecules are not flexible.

(3) That solvation is absent in the region of concentration studied, yet another condition to be fulfilled in applying Kuhn's equation, has been shown in a previous communication (Basu, *loc. cit.*).

Thus the three interfering factors, which might invalidate the calculation of a/b from viscometric point of view have been eliminated.

Fig. 2.

Fig. 3.

It has, however, to be remarked that all the measurements have been carried out in a capillary viscometer under high rates of shear, which might prevent free Brownian movement. This would cause the calculated a/b ratio to be greater than actual value, as could be verified in the case of tobacco mosaic virus by Frampton and Neurath (*loc. cit.*). The role of Brownian movement can be assessed only if measurements of flowing birefringence could be done with shellac solutions under identical condition. Thus the value of axial ratio obtained here cannot be taken as quantitative unless corroborated by other physical measurements viz., X-ray analysis, diffusion measurements, etc. Such diffusion measurements have been made and will be reported in a subsequent communication.

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